

Extension and layup optimization of Double-Double laminates based on lamination parameters

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ABSTRACT

Novel Double-Double (DD) laminates family provide a new solution for the design and optimization of composite structure. This article analyses the characteristics of the stiffness matrix of the extended DD laminates based on laminate parameters (LPs), and applies it to a classic benchmark problem. The explicit LPs expressions of extended DD laminates are first derived, and the explicit functions of the feasible region of the LPs are derived through the Lagrange multiplier method, which better explains the characteristics of the DD family mathematically. Subsequently, the classical 18-plane horseshoe benchmark problem is optimized based on the feasible region of DD LPs. The optimal solutions with blending constraint are analytically obtained, and the whole problem is summarized as a linear programming problem in LPs feasible region. The optimal solution is compared with the iterative solution obtained by evolutionary algorithm, which further illustrates the advantages of DD. The exploration of DD in this study can contribute to the discovery of new laminate families and promote the application of DD laminates.

1 INTRODUCTION

The traditional ply angles of laminates are usually 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° , which is also called QUAD. QUAD laminates contain a large number of permutations by changing the ply orientation of each layer. Flexible stacking sequence enables QUAD laminates to satisfy the majority of application requirements, but it also leads to the emergence of high-dimensional discrete design challenges. In order to solve this problem, in theory, researchers usually use the intermediate continuous variable: lamination parameters (LPs) to design the stacking sequence [1]. The advantages of using LPs are obvious. According to the classical lamination theory (CLT), each stiffness coefficient of the laminate can be expressed as a linear combination of laminate parameters. The ply numbers are integrated into LPs by orthogonalizing the thickness, which significantly reduces the number of design variables. When LPs are considered as independent variables, they are interrelated continuous design variables in the interval $[-1,1]$, it makes the optimization problem usually have a global optimal solution.

The discreteness of ply angle and the constraints of design criteria make the disadvantages of traditional QUAD laminates in layup optimization obvious: inefficient fiber layup, high calculation cost of optimization, complex strength calculation, etc. To overcome these disadvantages, Tsai [2] proposed a novel double-double (DD) laminate. DD laminate is composed of repeated stacking of a four-ply sublaminates, and its classical expression is $[\pm\Phi/\pm\Psi]_r$, where r is the number of repetitions. Research showed that when r is greater than or equal to 4, DD laminates are homogeneous and membrane/bending and bending/torsion coupling can be ignored [3]. Moreover, DD can achieve a simpler and larger taper ratio through the card sliding technology, and the manufacturing is simple and not prone to error. The properties and advantages of DD laminate have been widely studied, and have been applied in some structures.

The unique layup characteristic makes DD laminates have significant advantages in design and manufacturing. However, the current research mainly focuses on the performance test and layup design of classic DD laminates $[\pm\Phi/\pm\Psi]_r$. In theory, DD family also contains laminates with other layup characteristics. Therefore, breaking through the limitation of classical DD and analyzing DD family from a more general perspective will help the understanding and application of DD. In this paper, the

classical $[\pm\Phi/\pm\Psi]_r$ DD stacking sequence is extended to the general $[\theta_1/\theta_2/\dots/\theta_l]_r$ case. The lamination parameter expressions of the extended DD laminates are derived, and the corresponding feasible region is studied by using Lagrange multiplier method. Based on the obtained expressions, the laws of DD family are summarized. Then, the classical 18-panel horseshoe benchmark problem is optimized by using the LPs feasible region of DD, and the optimal solutions with/without blending constraint are analytically obtained. The results show that the optimal solutions are obtained at the lower bound of the feasible region, regardless of the categories of DD, and the results are compared with the iterative solutions obtained by evolutionary algorithm.

2 EXTENDED DD LAMINATES BASED ON LPS

2.1 Lamination parameters of general extended DD laminate

The extended DD laminates were first introduced in [3], and the ξ_1^A - ξ_2^A lamination parameter design spaces of two types of extended laminates $[\pm\Phi_m/\pm\Psi]_r$ and $[\pm\Phi/\pm\Psi/\theta]_r$ ($\theta \in \{0^\circ, 90^\circ\}$) were studied in [3] to illustrate the characteristics of classical $[\pm\Phi/\pm\Psi]_r$ DD laminates. However, the characteristics of extended DD laminates have not been further studied.

Fig. 1. Layup information of laminate. (a) Classical DD laminate, (b) General extended DD laminate.

In Fig. 1, a general DD extended laminate and a classical DD laminate are presented. In the classical DD laminate, it contains four types of layup categories, which are staggered 1: $[+\Phi/-\Psi/-\Phi/+\Psi]_r$, staggered 2: $[+\Phi/+\Psi/-\Phi/-\Psi]_r$, staggered 3: $[+\Phi/-\Psi/+\Psi/-\Phi]_r$, and staggered 4: $[\pm\Phi/\pm\Psi]_r$. When the specific stacking sequence is not considered, the sublaminate of the DD laminate has four angles, represented by θ_1 , θ_2 , θ_3 and θ_4 , respectively. Assuming the repetition number of the sublaminate is r and the thickness of each layer is t . The entire laminate contains $4r+1$ nodes, and the coordinates z corresponding to each node are shown in Fig. 1(a). In the general extended DD laminate, it is assumed that the sublaminate contains l layers. The total number of layers is lr , and the general laminate can be represented as $[\theta_1/\theta_2/\dots/\theta_l]_r$. The corresponding node coordinates z are related to the values of l and r , which are also shown in Fig. 1(b). Defining trigonometric functions $f_1(\theta) = \cos(2\theta)$, $f_2(\theta) = \cos(4\theta)$, $f_3(\theta) = \sin(2\theta)$ and $f_4(\theta) = \sin(4\theta)$. The lamination parameters $\xi_{[1,2,3,4]}^{A,B,D}$ of general extended DD laminate can be calculated as follows:

For $\xi_{[1,2,3,4]}^A$,

$$\xi_j^A = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^r \sum_{i=1}^l \int_{-1+2(lk-i-1)/lr}^{-1+2(lk-i)/lr} f_j(\theta_i) d\bar{z} \quad (1)$$

where $j = 1, 2, 3, 4$. Integrating each ply through the thickness and summing the repetition number k leads to,

$$\xi_j^A = \sum_{i=1}^l \frac{1}{l} f_j(\theta_i) \quad (2)$$

It can be seen that the value of ζ_j^A are only related to the type of sublaminar ply angle θ_i , and the contribution of each ply angle is equal.

Similarly, $\zeta_{[1,2,3,4]}^B$ can be obtained as

$$\zeta_j^B = \sum_{k=1}^r \sum_{i=1}^l \int_{-1+2(k-l+i-1)/lr}^{-1+2(k-l+i)/lr} \bar{z} f_j(\theta_i) d\bar{z} \quad (3)$$

Integrating each ply through the thickness and summing the repetition number k ,

$$\zeta_j^B = \sum_{i=1}^l \frac{2(-l+2i-1)}{l^2 r} f_j(\theta_i) \quad (4)$$

It can be seen that ζ_j^B are inversely proportional to the number of repetition number r . Therefore, increasing the number of plies results in the coupling stiffness matrix \mathbf{B} tending to $\mathbf{0}$. The type and stacking sequence of the sublaminar ply angles can affect the minimum value of r that required to satisfy the homogeneity criterion of DD laminate. Specific homogenization criterion is defined as [2],

$$|\mathbf{B}^*| < I^*(Q_{11} + Q_{22} + 2Q_{66}) \quad (5)$$

$$[\mathbf{A}^*] - [\mathbf{D}^*] < I^*(Q_{11} + Q_{22} + 2Q_{66}) \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{A}^*, \mathbf{B}^*, \mathbf{D}^* = \left[\frac{1}{h} \mathbf{A}, \frac{2}{h^2} \mathbf{B}, \frac{12}{h^3} \mathbf{D} \right] \quad (7)$$

where $Q_{11} + Q_{22} + 2Q_{66}$ is the Tasi modulus [4], I is the percentage of the Tasi modulus and is usually set to be 2%. $[\mathbf{A}^*, \mathbf{B}^*, \mathbf{D}^*]$ are the thickness normalized stiffnesses. Similarly, for $\zeta_{[1,2,3,4]}^D$,

$$\zeta_j^D = \frac{3}{2} \sum_{k=1}^r \sum_{i=1}^l \int_{-1+2(k-l+i-1)/lr}^{-1+2(k-l+i)/lr} \bar{z}^2 f_j(\theta_i) d\bar{z} \quad (8)$$

Integrating each ply through the thickness and summing the repetition number k leads to,

$$\zeta_j^D = \sum_{i=1}^l \left[\frac{1}{l} + 2 \frac{(l-i)^2 - (4i-3)(l-i) + (i-1)(i-2)}{l^3 r^2} \right] f_j(\theta_i) \quad (9)$$

It can be seen that ζ_j^D are inversely proportional to the square of the number of repetition number r . As the number of plies increases, the coefficient of $f_j(\theta_i)$ tends to be constant $1/l$, ζ_j^D tends to be equal to ζ_j^A . The angles of the sublaminar ply determine whether the values of the lamination parameters ζ_3^D, ζ_4^D can approach to 0.

2.2 The characteristics of general extended DD laminates

Each set of lamination parameters of general extended DD laminates can be obtained through an equation, as shown in Eqs. (2), (4), and (9). Through the study of these equations, the characteristics of extended DD laminate can be explored, which is also applicable to classical DD laminates.

In Eq. (2), the coefficients of each ply angle trigonometric function $f_j(\theta_i)$ are the same as $1/l$. However, in Eqs. (4) and (9), the coefficients of $f_j(\theta_i)$ are related to i , this indicates that the stacking sequence will affect the value of the coefficients, and it will further affect the minimum r value required for the laminate to satisfy the homogeneity. To illustrate the relationship between trigonometric function coefficient with stacking sequence, the following functions are defined:

$$\begin{cases} g_B(i) = \frac{2(-l+2i-1)}{l^2 r} \\ g_D(i) = \frac{1}{l} + 2 \frac{(l-i)^2 - (4i-3)(l-i) + (i-1)(i-2)}{l^3 r^2} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where $i \in [1, l, \mathbb{N}^*)$ represents the i -th ply of sublaminar in Fig. 1, l and r are positive integers. For sublaminar with the number of plies l , the sub-midplane coordinate is $lt/2$, and the number of i -th ply symmetrical about the sub-midplane is $l-i+1$. Substituting $l-i+1$ into Eq. (10), it can be obtained that:

$$\begin{cases} g_b(l-i+1) = \frac{2(l-2i+1)}{l^2 r} = -g_b(i) \\ g_D(l-i+1) = \frac{1}{l} + 2 \frac{(i-1)^2 - (4l-4i+1)(i-1) + (l-i)(l-i-1)}{l^3 r^2} = g_D(i) \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

It can be seen that in the sublaminar panel, the layers that are symmetrical about the sub-midplane contain opposite values of the ζ_j^B trigonometric coefficient, and the same values of the ζ_j^D trigonometric coefficient. Considering the coupling term coefficients $\zeta_{3,4}^A$, ζ_j^B and $\zeta_{3,4}^D$ in the LPs, combining Eq. (11) with Eqs. (2), (4) and (9), some characteristics of the general extended DD laminate can be obtained as follows:

- (1) When the sublaminar satisfies the balance constraint (with the same number of $+\theta$ and $-\theta$ angles), it can be obtained that $\zeta_{3,4}^A = 0$, and as the value of r increases, both ζ_j^B and $\zeta_{3,4}^D$ tend to 0. The balance of sublaminar is a sufficient and necessary condition for general extended DD laminates achieving homogenization.
- (2) When the sublaminar is antisymmetric about the sub-midplane, it can be obtained that $\zeta_{3,4}^{A,D} = 0$ and $\zeta_{1,2}^B = 0$.
- (3) When the sublaminar is symmetric about the sub-midplane, it can be obtained that $\zeta_j^B = 0$.

The essence of characteristics (2) and (3) is that for the general extended DD laminate, the laminate midplane coincides with the sub-midplane or is on the boundary of the sublaminar, as shown in Fig. 2. Therefore, when the sublaminar is antisymmetric or symmetric about the sub-midplane, the corresponding entire laminate will be antisymmetric or symmetric about the global midplane. In addition, a special type of fully decoupled ($\zeta_{3,4}^{A,D} = 0$, $\zeta_j^B = 0$) laminate can be derived from the above analysis results.

The trigonometric coefficients of Eq. (4) ζ_j^B have the following relationship:

$$g_b(1) + g_b\left(\frac{l}{2}\right) = \dots = g_b(i) + g_b\left(\frac{l}{2} - i + 1\right) = -\frac{2}{lr} \quad (12)$$

where the number of layers l in the sublaminar is even, and $i = 1, 2, \dots, l/2$. When the sublaminar satisfies feature (2) and the layers 1 to $l/2$ are balanced, ζ_3^B and ζ_4^B are also equal to 0. Therefore, the number of decoupled DD sublaminar layers should not be less than 8, and the basic expression is $[+\Psi/-\Psi/-\Psi/+ \Psi, -\Psi/+ \Psi/+ \Psi/-\Psi]_r$, or $[-\Psi/+ \Psi/+ \Psi/-\Psi, +\Psi/-\Psi/-\Psi/+ \Psi]_r$. The above two types of decoupled DD laminates were initially proposed by Miravete and Tasi [5], and this laminate family is called 'Metalite'. In this section, the mechanism of 'Metalite' laminate decoupling is explained from the analysis of lamination parameters of general extended DD laminate, and the laws are summarized.

Fig. 2. Relationship between sub-midplane and global midplane of general extended DD laminate.

2.3 Feasible region of extended DD laminate

Compared with QUAD layups, the complexity of the feasible region of DD laminate is reduced due to their simple stacking concept. In this section, based on the derived lamination parameters expressions, the ζ_1^A - ζ_2^A feasible region of extended laminates is mainly studied and summarized.

It is assumed that the layup of general extended laminate is balanced, including $l/2$ types of ply orientations (the number of sublaminar is even), and the layup is defined as $[\pm\theta_1/\pm\theta_2/\dots/\pm\theta_{l/2}]_r$. The Lagrange multiplier method is used to obtain the feasible region between two lamination parameters [6]:

$$H(\theta_1, \dots, \theta_{l/2}) = F(\theta_1, \dots, \theta_{l/2}) + \lambda(G(\theta_1, \dots, \theta_{l/2}) - x) \quad (13)$$

where F , G are two lamination parameters related to the layup orientation θ , and λ is a Lagrange multiplier. The solution of feasible region can be expressed as minimizing and maximizing $y = F(\theta_1, \dots, \theta_{l/2})$ subject to $x = G(\theta_1, \dots, \theta_{l/2})$. The conditions to be satisfied at each stationary point are:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial H}{\partial \theta_1} = \frac{\partial F}{\partial \theta_1} + \lambda \frac{\partial G}{\partial \theta_1} = 0 \\ \vdots \\ \frac{\partial H}{\partial \theta_{l/2}} = \frac{\partial F}{\partial \theta_{l/2}} + \lambda \frac{\partial G}{\partial \theta_{l/2}} = 0 \\ \frac{\partial H}{\partial \lambda} = G(\theta_1, \dots, \theta_{l/2}) - x = 0 \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

For the feasible region between the lamination parameters $\zeta_1^A - \zeta_2^A$, it can be seen from Eq. (2) that $\zeta_{1,2}^A$ are related to the types of layup orientations. According to the type and number of layup orientation variables, the feasible region of extended laminates can be roughly divided into the following three categories, and the corresponding characteristics can be further summarized.

Fig. 3. Feasible regions and boundary equations of $\zeta_1^A - \zeta_2^A$ for different categories of DD laminates. (a) Classic $[\pm\Phi/\pm\Psi]_r$, (b) $[(\pm\Phi)_m/(\pm\Psi)_m/\theta_n]_r$, (c) $[(\pm\Phi)_m/(\pm\Psi)_n]_r$, (d) $[(\pm\theta_1)/(\pm\theta_2)/\dots/(\pm\theta_{l/2})]_r$.

2.4.1 Feasible region of $[(\pm\Phi)_m/(\pm\Psi)_m/\theta_n]_r$

Firstly, the feasible region of extended DD laminates with two ply angle variables, Φ and Ψ , is considered. In the classic $[\pm\Phi/\pm\Psi]_r$ DD laminates, due to the special layup stacking, the $\zeta_1^A - \zeta_2^A$ LP feasible region is missing the area where 0° and 90° ply accounts for more than 50%, as shown on Fig. 3(a). In literature [3], $[0/90/\pm\Phi/\pm\Psi]_r$, $[\pm 45/\pm\Phi/\pm\Psi]_r$ and $[0/\pm\Phi/\pm\Psi]_r$ laminates were studied to explore areas outside the boundary. According to the characteristics of this kind of laminates, the general expression $[(\pm\Phi)_m/(\pm\Psi)_m/\theta_n]_r$ is given. Here m is the number of occurrences of $\pm\Phi$ and $\pm\Psi$ angles, θ_n is the known n ply angles, m and n are positive integers, satisfying the equation $4m+n = l$. According to Eq. (2), the expressions of lamination parameters ζ_1^A and ζ_2^A are given as follows:

$$\zeta_1^A = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \cos(2\theta_i)}{l} + \frac{2m}{l} (\cos 2\Phi + \cos 2\Psi) = b_1 + k(\cos 2\Phi + \cos 2\Psi) \quad (15)$$

$$\zeta_2^A = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \cos(4\theta_i)}{l} + \frac{2m}{l} (\cos 4\Phi + \cos 4\Psi) = b_2 + k(\cos 4\Phi + \cos 4\Psi) \quad (16)$$

The coefficients b, k ($\in(-1,1)$) are used to simplify the equation, which are independent of the ply angle variables Φ and Ψ , and can be considered as constants in the equation. According to the Lagrange multiplier method of Eqs. (13) and (14), the boundary equations are obtained as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\xi_2^A &\geq \frac{1}{k}(\xi_1^A - b_1)^2 - 2k + b_2, \quad \xi_1^A \in [b_1 - 2k, b_1 + 2k] \\ \xi_2^A &\leq \frac{2}{k}(\xi_1^A - b_1 + k)^2 + b_2, \quad \xi_1^A \in [b_1 - 2k, b_1] \\ \xi_2^A &\leq \frac{2}{k}(\xi_1^A - b_1 - k)^2 + b_2, \quad \xi_1^A \in [b_1, b_1 + 2k]\end{aligned}\quad (17)$$

Fig. 3(b) provides a schematic diagram of the obtained feasible region. According to the diagram and Eq. (17), it can be seen that, the feasible region of the general extended laminate $[(\pm\Phi)_m/(\pm\Psi)_n/\theta_n]_r$ is obtained by scaling and translating the feasible region of the classical $[\pm\Phi/\pm\Psi]_r$ laminate. The coefficient k determines the scaling size of the boundary parabolic equations on the x and y axes, while b_1 and b_2 determine the translation distance of the parabolas on the x and y axes, respectively.

2.4.2 Feasible region of $[(\pm\Phi)_m/(\pm\Psi)_n]_r$

When the number of ply angle variables Φ and Ψ is different, the general expression of laminate is $[(\pm\Phi)_m/(\pm\Psi)_n]_r$. Here m and n are the occurrence number of $\pm\Phi$ and $\pm\Psi$ angle pairs respectively, satisfying the equation $2m+2n = l$. The expressions of lamination parameters ξ_1^A and ξ_2^A are given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\xi_1^A &= \frac{2}{l}(m \cos 2\Phi + n \cos 2\Psi) \\ \xi_2^A &= \frac{2}{l}(m \cos 4\Phi + n \cos 4\Psi)\end{aligned}\quad (18)$$

When $m > n$, the boundary equations of the feasible region are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\xi_2^A &\geq 2(\xi_1^A)^2 - 1, \quad \xi_1^A \in [-1, 1] \\ \text{I: } \xi_2^A &\leq \frac{l}{n}(\xi_1^A + \frac{m}{m+n})^2 + \frac{m-n}{m+n}, \quad \xi_1^A \in [-1, \frac{n-m}{m+n}] \\ \text{II: } \xi_2^A &\leq \frac{l}{m}(\xi_1^A - \frac{n}{m+n})^2 + \frac{n-m}{m+n}, \quad \xi_1^A \in [\frac{n-m}{m+n}, 0] \\ \text{III: } \xi_2^A &\leq \frac{l}{m}(\xi_1^A + \frac{n}{m+n})^2 + \frac{n-m}{m+n}, \quad \xi_1^A \in [0, \frac{m-n}{m+n}] \\ \text{IV: } \xi_2^A &\leq \frac{l}{n}(\xi_1^A - \frac{m}{m+n})^2 + \frac{m-n}{m+n}, \quad \xi_1^A \in [\frac{m-n}{m+n}, 1]\end{aligned}\quad (19)$$

Fig. 3(c) provides the schematic diagram of the obtained feasible region. When $m < n$, the boundary equations of the feasible region are the m, n value exchange of the above formula. It can be seen from the diagram and Eq. (19) that the boundary constraint equations on the feasible region increase, and they are still parabolic. The values of m and n both determine the characteristics of the parabolas.

2.4.3 Feasible region of $[(\pm\theta_1)/(\pm\theta_2)/\dots/(\pm\theta_{l/2})]_r$

Further consider the increase of ply angle variable dimension. Assuming that the more general DD laminate contains $l/2$ ply angle variables, the expression of the laminate can be written as $[(\pm\theta_1)/(\pm\theta_2)/\dots/(\pm\theta_{l/2})]_r$. The corresponding lamination parameter ξ_1^A and ξ_2^A are given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\xi_1^A &= \frac{2}{l}(\cos 2\theta_1 + \cos 2\theta_2 + \dots + \cos 2\theta_{l/2}) \\ \xi_2^A &= \frac{2}{l}(\cos 4\theta_1 + \cos 4\theta_2 + \dots + \cos 4\theta_{l/2})\end{aligned}\quad (20)$$

The boundary equations of the feasible region are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\xi_2^A &\geq 2(\xi_1^A)^2 - 1, \quad \xi_1^A \in [-1, 1] \\ \xi_2^A &\leq \frac{4}{l} \left(\frac{l}{2} \xi_1^A + i - 1 \right)^2 + 1 - \frac{4}{l}, \quad \xi_1^A \in \left[\frac{-2i}{l}, \frac{4-2i}{l} \right] \\ \xi_2^A &\leq \frac{4}{l} \left(\frac{l}{2} \xi_1^A - i + 1 \right)^2 + 1 - \frac{4}{l}, \quad \xi_1^A \in \left[\frac{2i-4}{l}, \frac{2i}{l} \right]\end{aligned}\quad (21)$$

where i is an odd or even set, depending on the value of $l/2$. When $l/2$ is even, $i \in \{2, 4, \dots, l/2\}$, and when $l/2$ is odd, $i \in \{1, 3, \dots, l/2\}$. Fig. 3(d) provides a schematic diagram of the obtained feasible region. Combining Eq. (21), it can be seen that the upper boundary of the feasible region is a quadratic function related to the value of l . Due to the same number of each ply angle variable, $l/2$ parabolic lines with the same shape and different symmetry axes contain the equal interval span of ξ_1^A axis, evenly dividing the $[-1, 1]$ interval. When the value of l tends to infinity, the upper boundary of the whole feasible region is the straight line $\xi_2^A = 1$.

2.4.4 Summary of the feasible region for general extended DD laminates

The explicit expression of feasible region boundary equations and the comparison with classical DD laminate illustrate the characteristics of the aforementioned three types of extended DD laminates. In addition, some general conclusions regarding the ξ_1^A - ξ_2^A feasible region of extended DD laminate are summarized as follows:

(1) All the extended DD laminates have the same equation form for lamination parameters ξ_1^A and ξ_2^A , which can be expressed by a general expression, as shown in Eq. (22). Where m_i is the occurrence number of the i -th ply angle variable, d is the dimensionality of the variable, b_1 and b_2 are the coefficients corresponding to the known ply angles. When the research object is a combination of any two laminating parameters, similar expressions can still be obtained.

$$\xi_1^A = b_1 + \frac{2}{l} m_i \cos 2\theta_i, \quad \xi_2^A = b_2 + \frac{2}{l} m_i \cos 4\theta_i \quad (i \in \{1, 2, \dots, d\}) \quad (22)$$

(2) All boundary curve equations in the feasible region of ξ_1^A - ξ_2^A are quadratic functions. By combining Eqs. (14) and (22), it can be concluded that the shape of the feasible region is determined by the trigonometric function pairs $m_i \cos 2\theta_i$ - $m_i \cos 4\theta_i$. Therefore, adding known ply angles and proportionally changing the occurrence number of ply angle variables will only scale and translate the existing feasible region. Changing the proportion of the occurrence number of ply angle variables, and the dimensionality of the variables, the shape of the feasible region and the number of boundary equations will change, and the entire feasible domain space can be further expanded.

The general analysis and discussion of extended DD laminates from the perspective of laminate parameters and feasible region is helpful to further explain the characteristics of DD laminates from the theoretical level. From the above analysis, it can be concluded that increasing the variable dimension of sublaminates can expand the feasible region space of DD, and the gray feasible region of classical DD laminates in Fig. 3(a) can be further filled. However, in practical applications, the increase in the ply number of sublaminates will lead to the need for more plies to satisfy the homogeneity of laminates, which will affect the weight saving by tapering. In addition, with ply number increase in sublaminates, the appearance of ply drops corresponds to a higher taper ratio, and this may lead to high stress concentration [3]. The research on the homogeneity of the extended DD laminates will be carried out in our future work.

3 BUCKLING OPTIMIZATION OF HORSESHOE PROBLEM BASED ON DD LPS

3.1 Problem description

The 18-panel horseshoe configuration is shown in Fig. 4, the dimensions and local loadings of each panel are marked in the figure. All panels are assumed to be simply supported on four edges and loaded in bi-axial compression. The Graphite/Epoxy IM7/8552 unidirectional prepreg is used for each ply, where $E_1 = 141$ GPa (20.5 Msi), $E_2 = 9.03$ GPa (1.31 Msi), $G_{12} = 4.27$ GPa (0.62 Msi), $\nu_{12} = 0.32$, the ply thickness is 0.191mm (0.0075 in), and the prepreg density is 1.57g/cm³. The optimization objective is

to find the lightest horseshoe panel design without individual panel failure under buckling. A simply supported panel in bi-axial compression has a sinusoidal buckling mode. The panel is loaded such that critical buckling loads are $N_{xcr} = \lambda N_x$ and $N_{ycr} = \lambda N_y$, where λ is a scalar load amplitude factor. The value of λ corresponds to buckling is given by Eq. (23).

$$\lambda(m, n) = \frac{\pi^2 [D_{11}(m/a)^4 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})(m/a)^2(n/b)^2 + D_{22}(n/b)^4]}{(m/a)^2 N_x + (n/b)^2 N_y} \quad (23)$$

where m and n are the buckling half-wave numbers in the x and y directions respectively. a and b are the length and width dimensions of the plate. D_{11} , D_{12} , D_{66} , D_{22} are the bending stiffness coefficients of the laminated plate.

Fig. 4. Geometry and loads of 18-panel horseshoe optimization case [7].

3.2 DD optimization with blending constraint

When blending constraint is considered. The DD layup orientations of each plate are the same $[\pm\Phi/\pm\Psi]_1 = \dots = [\pm\Phi/\pm\Psi]_k = \dots = [\pm\Phi/\pm\Psi]_n$, and all plates have the same LPs. In this case, the design variables are the continuous layup angles and the plate thickness related to the number of layers.

Substituting the expression of the bending stiffness coefficients with respect to LPs into Eq. (23), Eq. (24) can be obtained. Here k_1 , k_2 and k_3 are constants related to the respective plate dimensions and applied loads, as shown in Eq. (25). U_1 - U_5 are the material stiffness invariants corresponding to IM7/8552 materials. The plate thickness h in Eq. (24) can be converted into Eq. (26). The optimization problem turns into obtaining the optimal LPs set that makes the total weight of the structure in Eq. (27) is minimized.

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda(m, n) &= \pi^2 [D_{11}k_1 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})k_2 + D_{22}k_3] \\ &= \frac{h^3}{12} \pi^2 [\xi_1^D U_2 (k_1 - k_3) + \xi_2^D U_3 (k_1 + k_3 - 6k_2) + (U_1 k_1 + U_1 k_3 + 2U_4 k_2 + 4U_5 k_2)] \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{h^3}{12} \pi^2 F(\xi_1^D, \xi_2^D) \\ &\begin{cases} k_1 = \frac{(m/a)^4}{(m/a)^2 N_x + (n/b)^2 N_y} \\ k_2 = \frac{(m/a)^2 (n/b)^2}{(m/a)^2 N_x + (n/b)^2 N_y} \\ k_3 = \frac{(n/b)^4}{(m/a)^2 N_x + (n/b)^2 N_y} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

$$h_i = \sqrt[3]{\frac{12}{\pi^2 F_i(\xi_1^D, \xi_2^D)}} \quad (26)$$

$$W = \sum_{i=1}^{18} \rho a_i b_i h_i = \rho [a_1 b_1 \sum_{i \in P_1} \sqrt[3]{\frac{12}{\pi^2 F_i(\xi_1^D, \xi_2^D)}} + a_3 b_3 \sum_{j \in P_2} \sqrt[3]{\frac{12}{\pi^2 F_j(\xi_1^D, \xi_2^D)}}] \quad (27)$$

$$\begin{cases} \frac{F_i(\xi_1^D, \xi_2^D)}{F_1(\xi_1^D, \xi_2^D)} = \frac{(m/a)^2(N_x)_1 + (n/b)^2(N_y)_1}{(m/a)^2(N_x)_i + (n/b)^2(N_y)_i} = k'_i, & i \in P_1 \\ \frac{F_j(\xi_1^D, \xi_2^D)}{F_3(\xi_1^D, \xi_2^D)} = \frac{(m/a)^2(N_x)_3 + (n/b)^2(N_y)_3}{(m/a)^2(N_x)_j + (n/b)^2(N_y)_j} = k'_j, & j \in P_2 \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

$$W = \rho (a_1 b_1 \sum_{i \in P_1} k'_i \sqrt[3]{\frac{1}{F_1(\xi_1^D, \xi_2^D)}} + a_3 b_3 \sum_{j \in P_2} k'_j \sqrt[3]{\frac{1}{F_3(\xi_1^D, \xi_2^D)}}) \quad (29)$$

The plates in the respective sets of \mathbf{P}_1 and \mathbf{P}_2 have the same size and LPs, it can be obtained from Eq. (24) and Eq. (25) that the function $F(\xi_1^D, \xi_2^D)$ corresponding to the plates in the two sets are proportional as shown in Eq. (28). Define the function $F(\xi_1^D, \xi_2^D)$ ratio of each plate in the \mathbf{P}_1 set with respect to plate 1 as k'_i , and define the function $F(\xi_1^D, \xi_2^D)$ ratio of each plate in the \mathbf{P}_2 set with respect to plate 3 as k'_j . The weight of the entire plate is only related to the function F corresponding to plates 1 and 3, as shown in Eq. (29). F_1 and F_3 are interrelated functions related to variables ξ_1^D and ξ_2^D . Therefore, minimizing the weight of the structure is equivalent to doing a linear program to find the minimum value on the feasible region composed of $\frac{1}{\sqrt[3]{F_1}}$ and $\frac{1}{\sqrt[3]{F_3}}$.

The linear programming of Eq. (29) in the feasible region of an extended DD laminate is shown in Fig. 5, where the boundary equations are implicitly derived from the section 2.3. It can be concluded that the minimum value of the structure weight is also obtained at the lower bound of the DD feasible region, and the optimal layups are also single DD. Since the number of layers is even, the optimal solution of LPs is the value interval. The optimal LPs values are $\xi_1^D \in [-0.166, -0.124]$, $\xi_2^D \in [-0.945, -0.969]$, and the optimal ply angles are single DD interval $[\pm 49.79^\circ, \pm 48.56^\circ]$.

Fig. 5. LPs optimal solution of benchmark problem with blending constraint in the feasible region of an extended DD laminate.

Table 1 shows the number of plies and buckling factor of each plate when the single DD ply angle taken as $\pm 49^\circ$. When the number of DD layers is rounded up to the even, the weight of the whole plate is 28.67kg, the residual buckling factor of each plate is also given in the table, and all plates satisfy the homogeneity criterion.

3.3 Results analysis and comparison

Based on the obtained lamination parameters and the feasible region design space of DD laminates, the optimization results of the classic horseshoe benchmark problem are derived analytically. Most of the previous studies used evolutionary algorithms to optimize the benchmark problem. In order to further reveal the characteristics and advantages of DD in layup optimization, the results of DD and evolutionary algorithm optimization are compared and analyzed.

Table 1 provides the optimization results of each plate based on PDS (ply drop sequence) layup strategy under genetic algorithm and compares them with DD optimization results with even number of plies satisfying blending constraint. PDS is a layup design method for internal ply drops proposed by Yang et al [8]. This method conveniently expresses layup information and realizes the satisfaction of blending constraint. Under the balanced and symmetrical design criteria, PDS selects QUAD ($0^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, 90^\circ$) and General ($0^\circ, \pm 15^\circ, \pm 30^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, \pm 60^\circ, \pm 75^\circ, 90^\circ$) two types of ply angles for optimization. When the PDS selects QUAD orientations and the number of layers is even, the optimal weight of the structure is 28.76kg after 2500 iterations optimization. As the current optimization algorithm with strong performance, the optimized solution obtained by PDS using QUAD layer is inferior to the solution obtained by DD satisfying the homogeneity optimization. In addition, the convergence time of the optimization algorithm iteration takes several hours, while DD only needs a few milliseconds to obtain the optimal solution. When PDS selects the General ply angle and the number of plies is allowed to be odd, the optimal weight of the structure is 28.47kg after 2800 iterations optimization, which is 0.29kg lighter than QUAD solution and better than DD solution.

Table 1. Results comparison for DD with PDS.

Panel	PDS (QUAD)		PDS (General)		DD	
	Ply number (even)	λ_{\min}	Ply number (odd)	λ_{\min}	Ply number (even)	λ_{\min}
1	34	1.166	33	1.019	34	1.130
2	28	1.051	29	1.106	28	1.011
3	22	1.117	23	1.331	22	1.194
4	20	1.223	19	1.109	20	1.306
5	16	1.034	16	1.102	16	1.014
6	22	1.004	23	1.196	22	1.073
7	20	1.184	19	1.074	20	1.265
8	26	1.110	23	1.032	26	1.195
9	38	1.037	39	1.092	38	1.015
10	36	1.135	35	1.000	36	1.103
11	30	1.111	30	1.055	30	1.072
12	28	1.046	29	1.101	28	1.007
13	22	1.051	23	1.252	22	1.123
14	20	1.297	18	1.003	18	1.010
15	26	1.075	25	1.000	26	1.159
16	32	1.063	31	1.035	32	1.199
17	20	1.201	19	1.089	20	1.283
18	24	1.179	23	1.085	24	1.263
Weight(kg)	28.76		28.47		28.67	

Fig. 6 shows the distribution of DD and PDS QUAD optimization solutions in the feasible region of $\xi_1^D - \xi_2^D$. The areas enclosed by the blue curve and black dotted line are DD feasible region and QUAD feasible region, respectively. The special stacking characteristic makes the optimal solution obtained by

DD unique. For QUAD laminates, in order to satisfy the blending constraint and ensure the continuity of the layup, the stacking sequence of each plate is different, and the solution set is distributed on the right side of the lower boundary of the feasible region. In theory, each plate approaches the theoretical optimal solution as closer as possible to minimize weight, but the discrete ply angle variables, blending constraint, and other design criteria make the solution values compromise and aggregate.

Fig. 6. Distribution of DD optimal solution and PDS QUAD optimal solution in feasible region of lamination parameters.

Fig. 7. Distribution of DD optimal solution and PDS General optimal solution in feasible region of lamination parameters.

Fig. 7 shows the distribution of DD and PDS General optimization solutions in the feasible region of $\xi_1^D - \xi_2^D$, where the area enclosed by the black dotted line is the General laminate feasible region. It can be seen from the figure that the optimal solutions obtained by using General ply angle are also distributed discretely at the lower boundary of the feasible region. However, compared with QUAD solutions, PDS General solutions are more concentrated and closed to DD solutions. This is because the increase of ply angle variables expands the feasible region, and the distribution of the optimal solution set is further optimized. Moreover, the number of plies can be taken as an odd number further utilize the buckling margin for design.

In this 18-plane benchmark problem, it can be concluded from the comparison of all optimization solutions that the dimension of ply angle variable and the existence of design constraints determine the optimization efficiency and convergence of the traditional optimization algorithm. The higher dimension of the ply angle variable brings larger feasible region design space, better solution and higher

computational cost, while the existence of design constraints could affect the distribution of solution set. When the coupling deformation is not desired and the better material homogeneity is expected. DD has obvious advantages over traditional QUAD laminates, including faster optimization efficiency, better solutions, simple and convenient manufacturing layups. Although lighter structural weight can be obtained by increasing the type of QUAD ply angles, the calculation cost and manufacturing difficulty also increase, and the complex internal ply drops will bring more design challenges.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the general extended DD laminates are analyzed and applied based on lamination parameters and feasible region. The explicit LPs expressions and feasible region of general extended DD laminates are derived, and the characteristics of DD laminates family are revealed. Based on the feasible region of extended DD lamination parameters, the classical 18-plane horseshoe benchmark problem is optimized. The conclusions of this paper are summarized as follows:

- (1) In the general extended DD laminate $[\theta_1/\theta_2/\dots/\theta]_r$. Lamination parameter ζ^A is only related to the type of sublaminates ply angles, and the ζ^B and ζ^D are inversely proportional to the number of sublaminates repetitions r and r^2 . When the value of r increases, ζ^B tends to 0, and the ζ^D tends to be equal to ζ^A . The balance of sublaminates is a sufficient and necessary condition for DD laminate family achieving homogenization, and the symmetry and antisymmetry of sublaminates can further directly eliminate coupling deformation.
- (2) The lamination parameters ζ_1^A and ζ_2^A of all extended DD laminates have the same equation form. In addition, all boundary curve equations in the feasible region of ζ_1^A - ζ_2^A are quadratic functions.
- (3) The classical 18-plane horseshoe benchmark problem is more intuitively optimized by using derived DD feasible regions. The whole problem is summarized as a linear programming problem in the LPs feasible region of DD, and the optimal solution is obtained at the lower bound of the feasible region, regardless of the categories of DD. When the blending constraint is considered, the optimal weight of the structure is 28.67kg, and the optimal DD layup is $[\pm 49^\circ]_r$.

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